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1
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4
5 %% Rated power -> blade radius
6 syms R_blade_sym
7
8 B      = 3;%Blade number
9 rho    = 1.225;%Air density kg/m^3
10 U_inf  = 11.4;%Freestream wind velocity,m/s
11 lambda = 7;%Tip Speed Ratio
12 theta_c = 0;%Control pitch angle, deg
13 C_p_target = 0.45;%Initial guess for power coefficient
14 D_hub   = 3;%Hub diameter, m
15 R_hub   = D_hub/2;%Hub radius,m
16 eta     = 0.9;%Gear box efficiency
17 Target_Power = 5e6;%Target rated power, W
18
19
20
21 P_rated_eqn = eta * C_p_target * 0.5 * rho * pi * (R_blade_sym^2 - R_hub^2) * U_inf^3 ==
    Target_Power;
22 R_solution = solve(P_rated_eqn, R_blade_sym);
23 R_blade = double(R_solution(R_solution > 0));
24
25 fprintf('-----\n');
26 fprintf('BLADE SIZING RESULTS\n');
27 fprintf('-----\n');
28 fprintf('Required blade radius: %.2f m\n', R_blade);
29
30 D_blade = R_blade*2;
31 RPM     = (60 * U_inf * lambda) / (pi * D_blade);
32 omega  = RPM * (2 * pi / 60);
33
34 fprintf('Rotor Diameter:      %.2f m\n', D_blade);
35 fprintf('Rated RPM:              %.2f rpm\n', RPM);
36 fprintf('Angular Velocity:       %.2f rad/s\n', omega);
37
38 r_hub = D_hub / 2;
39
40 %% Span discretization
41 nSeg = 35;
42 r_over_R = linspace(0.08, 1.0, nSeg);
43 r = r_over_R * R_blade;
44
45 lambda_r = lambda .* r_over_R;
46 phi = (2/3) .* atand(1 ./ lambda_r);
47
48 %% Compute max L/D for S813, S811, S812
49 computeMaxLD = @(alpha,CL,CD) localMaxLD(alpha,CL,CD);
50
51 try
52     S811 = NREL_s_S811_Airfoil_NREL_s_S811_Airfoil_Re6_000_M0_00_N9_0_360_M;
53     [maxLDS811, alpha_at_maxS811, CL_at_maxS811, CD_at_maxS811] = ...
54         computeMaxLD(S811.Alpha(:), S811.CL(:), S811.CD(:));
55 catch
56     warning('S811 data not found. Using placeholders. ');
57     CL_at_maxS811 = 1.0; CD_at_maxS811 = 0.01; alpha_at_maxS811 = 5;
58 end
59

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60 try
61     S812 = NREL_s_S812_Airfoil_NREL_s_S812_Airfoil_Re6_000_M0_00_N9_0_360_M;
62     [maxLDS812, alpha_at_maxS812, CL_at_maxS812, CD_at_maxS812] = ...
63         computeMaxLD(S812.Alpha(:), S812.CL(:), S812.CD(:));
64 catch
65     warning('S812 data not found. Using placeholders. ');
66     CL_at_maxS812 = 0.9; CD_at_maxS812 = 0.01; alpha_at_maxS812 = 4;
67 end
68
69 try
70     S813 = NREL_s_S813_Airfoil_NREL_s_S813_Airfoil_Re6_000_M0_00_N9_0_360_M;
71     [maxLDS813, alpha_at_maxS813, CL_at_maxS813, CD_at_maxS813] = ...
72         computeMaxLD(S813.Alpha(:), S813.CL(:), S813.CD(:));
73 catch
74     warning('S813 data not found. Using placeholders. ');
75     CL_at_maxS813 = 0.8; CD_at_maxS813 = 0.01; alpha_at_maxS813 = 3;
76 end
77
78 %% Airfoil Performance Plots
79 % For S811
80 figure('Color','w');
81 subplot(3,1,1);
82 plot(S811.Alpha, S811.CL, 'b-', 'LineWidth', 2);
83 xlabel('Alpha (deg)'); ylabel('CL'); title('CL vs Alpha - S811'); grid on;
84 subplot(3,1,2);
85 plot(S811.Alpha, S811.CD, 'r-', 'LineWidth', 2);
86 xlabel('Alpha (deg)'); ylabel('CD'); title('CD vs Alpha - S811'); grid on;
87 subplot(3,1,3);
88 plot(S811.Alpha, S811.CL ./ S811.CD, 'g-', 'LineWidth', 2);
89 xlabel('Alpha (deg)'); ylabel('CL/CD'); title('CL/CD vs Alpha - S811'); grid on;
90
91 % For S813
92 figure('Color','w');
93 subplot(3,1,1);
94 plot(S813.Alpha, S813.CL, 'b-', 'LineWidth', 2);
95 xlabel('Alpha (deg)'); ylabel('CL'); title('CL vs Alpha - S813'); grid on;
96 subplot(3,1,2);
97 plot(S813.Alpha, S813.CD, 'r-', 'LineWidth', 2);
98 xlabel('Alpha (deg)'); ylabel('CD'); title('CD vs Alpha - S813'); grid on;
99 subplot(3,1,3);
100 plot(S813.Alpha, S813.CL ./ S813.CD, 'g-', 'LineWidth', 2);
101 xlabel('Alpha (deg)'); ylabel('CL/CD'); title('CL/CD vs Alpha - S813'); grid on;
102
103 % For S812
104 figure('Color','w');
105 subplot(3,1,1);
106 plot(S812.Alpha, S812.CL, 'b-', 'LineWidth', 2);
107 xlabel('Alpha (deg)'); ylabel('CL'); title('CL vs Alpha - S812'); grid on;
108 subplot(3,1,2);
109 plot(S812.Alpha, S812.CD, 'r-', 'LineWidth', 2);
110 xlabel('Alpha (deg)'); ylabel('CD'); title('CD vs Alpha - S812'); grid on;
111 subplot(3,1,3);
112 plot(S812.Alpha, S812.CL ./ S812.CD, 'g-', 'LineWidth', 2);
113 xlabel('Alpha (deg)'); ylabel('CL/CD'); title('CL/CD vs Alpha - S812'); grid on;
114
115
116 %% Airfoil assignment for blade regions
117 CL = zeros(size(r_over_R));
118 CD = zeros(size(r_over_R));
119 alpha = zeros(size(r_over_R));
120

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121 for i = 1:numel(r_over_R)
122     if r_over_R(i) >= 0.08 && r_over_R(i) <= 0.3
123         CL(i)    = CL_at_maxS811;
124         CD(i)    = CD_at_maxS811;
125         alpha(i) = alpha_at_maxS811;
126     %elseif r_over_R(i) > 0.3 && r_over_R(i) <= 0.7
127         % CL(i)    = CL_at_maxS812;
128         % CD(i)    = CD_at_maxS812;
129         %alpha(i) = alpha_at_maxS812;
130     elseif r_over_R(i) > 0.3 && r_over_R(i) <= 1.0
131         CL(i)    = CL_at_maxS813;
132         CD(i)    = CD_at_maxS813;
133         alpha(i) = alpha_at_maxS813;
134     end
135 end
136
137 %% Chord distribution (DESIGN)
138 c = zeros(size(r_over_R));
139 for i = 1:numel(r_over_R)
140     c(i) = (8*pi*r_over_R(i)*R_blade) / (B*CL(i)) * (1 - cosd(phi(i)));
141 end
142
143 %% Blade solidity
144 sigma = zeros(size(r_over_R));
145 for i = 1:numel(r_over_R)
146     sigma(i) = (B*c(i)) / (2*pi*r(i));
147 end
148
149 %% Axial and angular induction factors
150 a = zeros(size(r_over_R));
151 for i = 1:numel(r_over_R)
152     a(i) = 1./(4*sind(phi(i))^2./(sigma(i)*CL(i)*cosd(phi(i))) + 1);
153 end
154 a_prime = (1 - 3.*a)./(4.*a - 1);
155
156 %% Twist distribution (DESIGN)
157 theta_p = phi - alpha;
158 theta_t = theta_p - theta_c;
159
160 %% Tip losses (DESIGN)
161 F = zeros(size(r_over_R));
162 for i = 1:numel(r_over_R)
163     exponent = - ( (B/2*(1 - (r(i)/R_blade))) / ((r(i)/R_blade)*sind(phi(i))) );
164     F(i) = 2/pi * acos( exp( exponent ) );
165 end
166 F(isnan(F)) = 0;
167 F = real(F);
168
169 %% Step change in local TSR
170 delta_lambda_r = zeros(size(r_over_R));
171 for i = 1:numel(r_over_R)
172     if i == 1
173         delta_lambda_r(i) = lambda_r(i) - 0;
174     else
175         delta_lambda_r(i) = lambda_r(i) - lambda_r(i-1);
176     end
177 end
178
179 %% Power coefficient Distribution (Design Point) (DESIGN)
180 C_pr = zeros(size(r_over_R));
181 for i = 1:numel(r_over_R)

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182     phi_rad = deg2rad(phi(i));
183
184     term1 = 8 * delta_lambda_r(i) / (lambda^2);
185     term2 = F(i) * sin(phi_rad)^2;
186     term3 = (cos(phi_rad) - lambda_r(i)*sin(phi_rad));
187     term4 = (sin(phi_rad) + lambda_r(i)*cos(phi_rad));
188     term5 = (1 - (CD(i)/CL(i)) * cot(phi_rad));
189     term6 = lambda_r(i)^2;
190
191     C_pr(i) = term1 * term2 * term3 * term4 * term5 * term6;
192 end
193
194 Overall_Cp_Design = sum(C_pr);
195 fprintf('Overall Power Coefficient (Design Lambda=%.1f): %.4f\n', lambda,
Overall_Cp_Design);
196
197 %% Differential calculations (Forces)
198 dr = zeros(size(r));
199 for i = 1:numel(r)
200     if i == 1
201         dr(i) = r(2) - r(1);
202     elseif i == numel(r)
203         dr(i) = r(i) - r(i-1);
204     else
205         dr(i) = (r(i+1) - r(i-1))/2;
206     end
207 end
208
209 U_rel = U_inf*(1-a)./sind(phi);
210
211 dF_l = CL.*0.5.*rho.*U_rel.^2.*c.*dr;%Differential lift force, N
212 dF_d = CD.*0.5.*rho.*U_rel.^2.*c.*dr;%Differential drag force, N
213 dF_n = dF_l.*cosd(phi) + dF_d.*sind(phi);%Differential normal force, N
214 dF_t = dF_l.*sind(phi) - dF_d.*cosd(phi);%Differential tangential force, N
215 dQ = 4.*F.*a_prime.*(1-a)*rho*U_inf*pi.*r.^3.*dr;%Differential torque, N*m
216 dT = 4.*F.*a.*(1-a)*rho*U_inf^2*pi.*r.*dr;%Differential thrust force, N
217 dPower = omega.*dQ;%Differential power
218
219 Power_total = sum(dPower);
220 fprintf('Total Power Calculated (BEM Integration): %.2f MW\n', Power_total/1e6);
221
222 %% Table of differential values
223 diff_table = table(r_over_R', r', dF_l', dF_d', dF_n', dF_t', dQ', dT', dPower', ...
224     'VariableNames', {'r_over_R', 'r', 'dF_l', 'dF_d', 'dF_n', 'dF_t', 'dQ', 'dT',
'dPower'});
225 disp('Table of Differential Values:');
226 disp(diff_table);
227
228 %% Plot differential values vs radial position
229 figure('Color','w', 'Name', 'Differential Values vs r/R');
230 subplot(3,3,1); plot(r_over_R, dF_l, 'LineWidth', 1.5); title('dF_l vs r/R'); xlabel('r/
R'); ylabel('dF_l (N)'); grid on;
231 subplot(3,3,2); plot(r_over_R, dF_d, 'LineWidth', 1.5); title('dF_d vs r/R'); xlabel('r/
R'); ylabel('dF_d (N)'); grid on;
232 subplot(3,3,3); plot(r_over_R, dF_n, 'LineWidth', 1.5); title('dF_n vs r/R'); xlabel('r/
R'); ylabel('dF_n (N)'); grid on;
233 subplot(3,3,4); plot(r_over_R, dF_t, 'LineWidth', 1.5); title('dF_t vs r/R'); xlabel('r/
R'); ylabel('dF_t (N)'); grid on;
234 subplot(3,3,5); plot(r_over_R, dQ, 'LineWidth', 1.5); title('dQ vs r/R'); xlabel('r/R');
ylabel('dQ (N m)'); grid on;

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235 subplot(3,3,6); plot(r_over_R, dT, 'LineWidth', 1.5); title('dT vs r/R'); xlabel('r/R');
    ylabel('dT (N)'); grid on;
236 subplot(3,3,7); plot(r_over_R, dPower, 'LineWidth', 1.5); title('dPower vs r/R');
    xlabel('r/R'); ylabel('dPower (W)'); grid on;
237
238 %% Table of sums
239 total_dF_l = sum(dF_l);
240 total_dF_d = sum(dF_d);
241 total_dF_n = sum(dF_n);
242 total_dF_t = sum(dF_t);
243 total_dQ = sum(dQ);
244 total_dT = sum(dT);
245 total_dPower = sum(dPower);
246
247 sum_table = table({'Total dF_l'; 'Total dF_d'; 'Total dF_n'; 'Total dF_t'; 'Total dQ';
    'Total dT'; 'Total dPower'}, ...
248     [total_dF_l; total_dF_d; total_dF_n; total_dF_t; total_dQ; total_dT; total_dPower],
    ...
249     'VariableNames', {'Quantity', 'Sum'});
250 disp('Table of Sums:');
251 disp(sum_table);
252
253 %% Linearized chord and twist distribution
254 b_1 = 2.5;
255 a_1 = 0.05;
256 a_2 = 0.10;
257
258 c_lin = zeros(size(r_over_R));
259 theta_t_lin = zeros(size(r_over_R));
260
261 for i = 1:numel(r_over_R)
262     c_lin(i) = a_1*(R_blade - r(i)) + b_1;
263     theta_t_lin(i) = a_2*(R_blade - r(i));
264 end
265
266 c_lin = max(c_lin, 0.05);
267
268
269 %% Calculate Cp for Linearized Blade at Design TSR
270 fprintf('\n-----\n');
271 fprintf('LINEARIZED BLADE ANALYSIS\n');
272 fprintf('-----\n');
273
274 % Recalculate solidity with linearized chord
275 sigma_lin = zeros(size(r_over_R));
276 for i = 1:numel(r_over_R)
277     sigma_lin(i) = (B*c_lin(i)) / (2*pi*r(i));
278 end
279
280 % Recalculate induction factors with linearized geometry
281 a_lin = zeros(size(r_over_R));
282 for i = 1:numel(r_over_R)
283     a_lin(i) = 1/(4*sind(phi(i))^2/(sigma_lin(i)*CL(i)) + 1);
284 end
285
286 % Recalculate tip losses with linearized twist
287 phi_lin = theta_t_lin + theta_c + alpha;
288 F_lin = zeros(size(r_over_R));
289 for i = 1:numel(r_over_R)
290     exponent = - ( (B/2*(1 - (r(i)/R_blade))) / ((r(i)/R_blade)*sind(phi_lin(i))) );
291     F_lin(i) = 2/pi * acos( exp( exponent ) );

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292 end
293 F_lin(isnan(F_lin)) = 0;
294 F_lin = real(F_lin);
295
296 % Calculate Cp distribution for linearized blade
297 C_pr_lin = zeros(size(r_over_R));
298 for i = 1:numel(r_over_R)
299     phi_rad_lin = deg2rad(phi_lin(i));
300
301     term1 = 8 * delta_lambda_r(i) / (lambda^2);
302     term2 = F_lin(i) * sin(phi_rad_lin)^2;
303     term3 = (cos(phi_rad_lin) - lambda_r(i)*sin(phi_rad_lin));
304     term4 = (sin(phi_rad_lin) + lambda_r(i)*cos(phi_rad_lin));
305     term5 = (1 - (CD(i)/CL(i)) * cot(phi_rad_lin));
306     term6 = lambda_r(i)^2;
307
308     C_pr_lin(i) = term1 * term2 * term3 * term4 * term5 * term6;
309 end
310
311 Overall_Cp_Linearized = sum(C_pr_lin);
312 fprintf('Overall Power Coefficient (Linearized Blade, Lambda=%.1f): %.4f\n', lambda,
Overall_Cp_Linearized);
313
314 %% TSR SWEEP
315 TSR_range = 3:0.5:12;
316
317 Cp_design_curve = zeros(size(TSR_range));
318 Cp_lin_curve     = zeros(size(TSR_range));
319
320 fprintf('\nCalculating Cp vs TSR for (1) design geometry and (2) linearized
geometry...\n');
321
322 for k = 1:numel(TSR_range)
323     lam_k = TSR_range(k);
324
325     Cp_design_curve(k) = computeCpFixedGeom( ...
326         lam_k, B, r_over_R, CL, CD, ...
327         @(lamr) (2/3).*atand(1./lamr) );
328 end
329
330 for k = 1:numel(TSR_range)
331     lam_k = TSR_range(k);
332     Cp_lin_curve(k) = computeCpFixedGeom( ...
333         lam_k, B, r_over_R, CL, CD, ...
334         @(lamr) (2/3).*atand(1./lamr) );
335 end
336
337 Cp_opt_proxy = max(Cp_design_curve) * ones(size(TSR_range));
338 fprintf('Proxy optimal Cp over TSR range (max of computed Cp curve): %.4f\n',
max(Cp_design_curve));
339
340 %% Differential calculations for LINEARIZED geometry
341 U_inf2 = 10;%Operational wind speed (wind speed used for the Qblade simulation)
342 U_rel_lin = U_inf2*(1-a_lin)./sind(phi_lin);
343
344 dF_l_lin = CL.*0.5.*rho.*U_rel_lin.^2.*c_lin.*dr;
345 dF_d_lin = CD.*0.5.*rho.*U_rel_lin.^2.*c_lin.*dr;
346 dF_n_lin = dF_l_lin.*cosd(phi_lin) + dF_d_lin.*sind(phi_lin);
347 dF_t_lin = dF_l_lin.*sind(phi_lin) - dF_d_lin.*cosd(phi_lin);
348 dQ_lin = 4.*F_lin.*a_prime.*(1-a_lin)*rho*U_inf2*pi.*r.^3.*dr;
349 dT_lin = 4.*F_lin.*a_lin.*(1-a_lin)*rho*U_inf2^2*pi.*r.*dr;

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350 dPower_lin = omega.*dQ_lin;
351
352 Power_total_lin = sum(dPower_lin);
353 fprintf('\nTotal Power Calculated (Linearized BEM Integration): %.2f MW\n',
Power_total_lin/1e6);
354
355 %% Table of differential values for LINEARIZED blade
356 diff_table_lin = table(r_over_R', r', dF_l_lin', dF_d_lin', dF_n_lin', dF_t_lin',
dQ_lin', dT_lin', dPower_lin', ...
357     'VariableNames', {'r_over_R', 'r', 'dF_l', 'dF_d', 'dF_n', 'dF_t', 'dQ', 'dT',
'dPower'});
358 disp('Table of Differential Values (Linearized Blade):');
359 disp(diff_table_lin);
360
361 %% Table of sums for LINEARIZED blade
362 total_dF_l_lin = sum(dF_l_lin);
363 total_dF_d_lin = sum(dF_d_lin);
364 total_dF_n_lin = sum(dF_n_lin);
365 total_dF_t_lin = sum(dF_t_lin);
366 total_dQ_lin = sum(dQ_lin);
367 total_dT_lin = sum(dT_lin);
368 total_dPower_lin = sum(dPower_lin);
369
370 sum_table_lin = table({'Total dF_l'; 'Total dF_d'; 'Total dF_n'; 'Total dF_t'; 'Total
dQ'; 'Total dT'; 'Total dPower'}, ...
371     [total_dF_l_lin; total_dF_d_lin; total_dF_n_lin; total_dF_t_lin; total_dQ_lin;
total_dT_lin; total_dPower_lin], ...
372     'VariableNames', {'Quantity', 'Sum'});
373 disp('Table of Sums (Linearized Blade):');
374 disp(sum_table_lin);
375
376 %% PLOTTING & VISUALIZATION
377
378 % Cp comparison vs TSR
379 figure('Color','w');
380 plot(TSR_range, Cp_design_curve, 'b-o', 'LineWidth', 2, 'MarkerFaceColor', 'b'); hold on;
381 plot(TSR_range, Cp_lin_curve, 'm-s', 'LineWidth', 2, 'MarkerFaceColor', 'm');
382 plot(TSR_range, Cp_opt_proxy, 'k--', 'LineWidth', 2);
383 grid on;
384 xlabel('Tip Speed Ratio (\lambda)');
385 ylabel('Power Coefficient (C_p)');
386 title('C_p vs TSR: Design Geometry vs Linearized Geometry (and Proxy Optimal)');
387 xline(lambda, 'r--', 'Design \lambda');
388 legend('C_p (Design)', 'C_p (Linearized)', 'C_{p,opt} proxy (max over TSR)', 'Location',
'best');
389
390 % Geometry comparison (design vs linearized)
391 figure('Color','w');
392 subplot(2,1,1);
393 plot(r_over_R, c, 'b-', 'LineWidth', 2); hold on;
394 plot(r_over_R, c_lin, 'm--', 'LineWidth', 2);
395 grid on; xlabel('r/R'); ylabel('Chord (m)');
396 title('Chord Distribution: Design vs Linearized');
397 legend('Design chord', 'Linearized chord', 'Location','best');
398
399 subplot(2,1,2);
400 plot(r_over_R, theta_t, 'r-', 'LineWidth', 2); hold on;
401 plot(r_over_R, theta_t_lin, 'k--', 'LineWidth', 2);
402 grid on; xlabel('r/R'); ylabel('Twist (deg)');
403 title('Twist Distribution: Design vs Linearized');
404 legend('Design twist', 'Linearized twist', 'Location','best');

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405
406 % Differential Forces
407 figure('Color','w');
408 subplot(2,1,1)
409 plot(r_over_R, dF_n, 'g-', 'LineWidth', 1.5); hold on;
410 plot(r_over_R, dF_t, 'm-', 'LineWidth', 1.5);
411 ylabel('Force per segment (N)'); xlabel('r/R');
412 legend('Normal Force', 'Tangential Force');
413 title('Differential Forces');
414 grid on;
415
416 subplot(2,1,2)
417 plot(r_over_R, C_pr, 'k-', 'LineWidth', 1.5);
418 ylabel('Local Power Coeff Contribution'); xlabel('r/R');
419 title('Local C_p Distribution at Design \lambda');
420 grid on;
421
422 % Differential Torque vs r/R for Optimized Blade
423 figure('Color','w');
424 plot(r_over_R, dQ, 'b-', 'LineWidth', 2);
425 xlabel('r/R');
426 ylabel('Differential Torque (N m)');
427 title('Differential Torque vs Non-Dimensional Radial Position for Optimized Blade');
428 grid on;
429
430 %% 3D BLADE MODEL GENERATION - DESIGN GEOMETRY
431 nAirfoilPts = 60;
432 x_af = [linspace(1, 0, nAirfoilPts/2), linspace(0, 1, nAirfoilPts/2)]';
433 yt_af = 0.2;
434 y_af = [0.6*sqrt(x_af(1:nAirfoilPts/2)).*(1-x_af(1:nAirfoilPts/2)); ...
435         -0.6*sqrt(x_af(nAirfoilPts/2+1:end)).*(1-x_af(nAirfoilPts/2+1:end))];
436 x_af = x_af - 0.25;
437
438 X_blade = zeros(nAirfoilPts, nSeg);
439 Y_blade = zeros(nAirfoilPts, nSeg);
440 Z_blade = zeros(nAirfoilPts, nSeg);
441
442 for i = 1:nSeg
443     chord_local = c(i);
444     twist_local = theta_t(i);
445     r_local      = r(i);
446
447     x_scaled = x_af * chord_local;
448     y_scaled = y_af * chord_local;
449
450     twist_rad = deg2rad(twist_local);
451     x_rot = x_scaled * cos(twist_rad) - y_scaled * sin(twist_rad);
452     y_rot = x_scaled * sin(twist_rad) + y_scaled * cos(twist_rad);
453
454     X_blade(:, i) = x_rot;
455     Y_blade(:, i) = r_local;
456     Z_blade(:, i) = y_rot;
457 end
458
459 figure('Color','w', 'Position', [100, 100, 800, 600]);
460 surf(X_blade, Y_blade, Z_blade, 'FaceColor', [0.3 0.6 0.9], 'EdgeColor', 'none',
461      'FaceAlpha', 1.0);
462 light; lighting gouraud;
463 xlabel('Chordwise (m)'); ylabel('Spanwise (m)'); zlabel('Thickness (m)');
464 title('3D Blade Geometry - Design');
465 axis equal; view(120, 30); grid on;

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```

465
466 figure('Color','w', 'Position', [150, 150, 800, 800]);
467 colors = lines(B);
468 for b_idx = 1:B
469     angle_offset = (b_idx-1) * (2*pi/B);
470
471     X_r = Y_blade .* cos(angle_offset) - X_blade .* sin(angle_offset);
472     Y_r = Y_blade .* sin(angle_offset) + X_blade .* cos(angle_offset);
473     Z_r = Z_blade;
474
475     surf(X_r, Y_r, Z_r, 'FaceColor', colors(b_idx,:), 'EdgeColor', 'none', 'FaceAlpha',
0.9);
476     hold on;
477 end
478 axis equal; grid on;
479 xlabel('X (m)'); ylabel('Y (m)'); zlabel('Z (m)');
480 title(sprintf('Full Rotor: %d Blades, D = %.1f m - Design Geometry', B, D_blade));
481 view(3); light; lighting gouraud;
482
483 %% 3D BLADE MODEL GENERATION - LINEARIZED GEOMETRY
484 X_blade_lin = zeros(nAirfoilPts, nSeg);
485 Y_blade_lin = zeros(nAirfoilPts, nSeg);
486 Z_blade_lin = zeros(nAirfoilPts, nSeg);
487
488 for i = 1:nSeg
489     chord_local = c_lin(i);
490     twist_local = theta_t_lin(i);
491     r_local      = r(i);
492
493     x_scaled = x_af * chord_local;
494     y_scaled = y_af * chord_local;
495
496     twist_rad = deg2rad(twist_local);
497     x_rot = x_scaled * cos(twist_rad) - y_scaled * sin(twist_rad);
498     y_rot = x_scaled * sin(twist_rad) + y_scaled * cos(twist_rad);
499
500     X_blade_lin(:, i) = x_rot;
501     Y_blade_lin(:, i) = r_local;
502     Z_blade_lin(:, i) = y_rot;
503 end
504
505 figure('Color','w', 'Position', [200, 200, 800, 600]);
506 surf(X_blade_lin, Y_blade_lin, Z_blade_lin, 'FaceColor', [0.9 0.3 0.6], 'EdgeColor',
'none', 'FaceAlpha', 1.0);
507 light; lighting gouraud;
508 xlabel('Chordwise (m)'); ylabel('Spanwise (m)'); zlabel('Thickness (m)');
509 title('3D Blade Geometry - Linearized');
510 axis equal; view(120, 30); grid on;
511
512 figure('Color','w', 'Position', [250, 250, 800, 800]);
513 colors_lin = lines(B);
514 for b_idx = 1:B
515     angle_offset = (b_idx-1) * (2*pi/B);
516
517     X_r = Y_blade_lin .* cos(angle_offset) - X_blade_lin .* sin(angle_offset);
518     Y_r = Y_blade_lin .* sin(angle_offset) + X_blade_lin .* cos(angle_offset);
519     Z_r = Z_blade_lin;
520
521     surf(X_r, Y_r, Z_r, 'FaceColor', colors_lin(b_idx,:), 'EdgeColor', 'none',
'FaceAlpha', 0.9);
522     hold on;

```

```

523 end
524 axis equal; grid on;
525 xlabel('X (m)'); ylabel('Y (m)'); zlabel('Z (m)');
526 title(sprintf('Full Rotor: %d Blades, D = %.1f m - Linearized Geometry', B, D_blade));
527 view(3); light; lighting gouraud;
528
529 %% ----- Local functions -----
530
531 function [maxLD, alphaAtMax, CLAtMax, CDAtMax] = localMaxLD(alpha, CL, CD)
532 alpha = alpha(:);
533 CL     = CL(:);
534 CD     = CD(:);
535
536 valid = isfinite(alpha) & isfinite(CL) & isfinite(CD) & (CD > 0);
537
538 LD = nan(size(CD));
539 LD(valid) = CL(valid) ./ CD(valid);
540
541 [maxLD, idx] = max(LD, [], 'omitnan');
542
543 if isempty(idx) || ~isfinite(maxLD)
544     alphaAtMax = NaN;
545     CLAtMax    = NaN;
546     CDAtMax    = NaN;
547 else
548     alphaAtMax = alpha(idx);
549     CLAtMax    = CL(idx);
550     CDAtMax    = CD(idx);
551 end
552 end
553
554 function Cp = computeCpFixedGeom(lam_k, B, r_over_R, CL, CD, phiApproxFcn)
555 lam_r_k = lam_k .* r_over_R;
556
557 phi_k_deg = phiApproxFcn(lam_r_k);
558 phi_k_rad = deg2rad(phi_k_deg);
559
560 F_k = zeros(size(r_over_R));
561 for i = 1:numel(r_over_R)
562     if phi_k_rad(i) == 0 || r_over_R(i) == 0
563         F_k(i) = 0;
564     else
565         exponent = - ( (B/2*(1 - r_over_R(i))) / (r_over_R(i)*sin(phi_k_rad(i))) );
566         F_k(i) = 2/pi * acos( exp( exponent ) );
567     end
568 end
569 F_k(isnan(F_k)) = 0; F_k = real(F_k);
570
571 d_lam_r_k = zeros(size(r_over_R));
572 for i = 1:numel(r_over_R)
573     if i == 1, d_lam_r_k(i) = lam_r_k(i);
574     else,     d_lam_r_k(i) = lam_r_k(i) - lam_r_k(i-1);
575     end
576 end
577
578 C_pr_k = zeros(size(r_over_R));
579 for i = 1:numel(r_over_R)
580     term1 = 8 * d_lam_r_k(i) / (lam_k^2);
581     term2 = F_k(i) * sin(phi_k_rad(i))^2;
582     term3 = (cos(phi_k_rad(i)) - lam_r_k(i)*sin(phi_k_rad(i)));
583     term4 = (sin(phi_k_rad(i)) + lam_r_k(i)*cos(phi_k_rad(i)));

```

```

584     term5 = (1 - (CD(i)/CL(i)) * cot(phi_k_rad(i)));
585     term6 = lam_r_k(i)^2;
586
587     C_pr_k(i) = term1 * term2 * term3 * term4 * term5 * term6;
588 end
589
590 Cp = sum(C_pr_k);
591 end
592
593 %% Actual power
594 % Calculate the actual power based on the computed coefficients
595 C_p_lin = sum(C_pr_lin);
596 fprintf('Actual Power coefficient for linearized blade: %.2f \n', C_p_lin);
597
598 power = C_p_lin * eta * 0.5 * rho * pi * (R_blade^2 - R_hub^2) * U_inf^3; % where rho is
air density, A is the rotor area, and V is wind speed
599 fprintf('Actual Power Output for linearized blade: %.2f W\n', power);
600
601

```